

Giant Tumor of the Thigh Type Epithelioid Sarcoma of the Soft Tissues: A Rare Case with Literature Review

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Abstract :- Epithelioid sarcoma is a rare malignant tumor whose vital prognosis is unfavorable(1)(2), immunohistochemistry is the key examination for positive diagnosis(1)(3).

The treatment is mainly surgical and must be oncological, a supplement by radiotherapy can be proposed. We report a case report of a patient with a giant tumor of thigh , the biopsy reveal Epithelioid sarcoma , and we realised a carcinological resection.

Keywords:- Sarcoma-surgery-MRI-biopsy-tumor

I. INTRODUCTION

Sarcomas represent 1% of all malignant tumors in adults(1)(2).

Epithelioid sarcomas are rare mesenchymal tumors of unknown history and have multidirectional differentiation, which is mainly epithelial. They represent less than 1 % of all the sarcomas of soft tissues and generally have slow growth, with maximum incidence in young adult men and mainly occur in the extremities(3).

We report the case of a patient that we have taken care of at the Ibn Sina Hospital in Rabat, with the review of the literature.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

A 65 -year -old patient that we have taken care of at Ibn Sina Hospital in Rabat, for a giant swelling of the left thigh, which histology with complement of immunohistochemistry, came back in favor of an epithelioid sarcoma.

We will detail the therapeutic management which the patient has undergone, as well as the clinical evolution and we will refer to the literature.

He is a 65 -year -old patient, hypertensive and monitored for von Recklinghausen's disease. Upon examination, we found a mass of the antero-external face in its proximal portion of the left thigh(image 1-2), without signs of vascular compression or neurological suffering, all evolving in a context of atmosphere encrypted at 12kg.

Standard X-ray of the pelvis and femur did not show any bone abnormalities. An exploration by MRI shows an antero-lateral mass of two thirds of the left thigh of 30*19cm in T1/T2 hypersignal and which is enhanced with the gadolinium, with multiple inguinal adenopathies. The vessels and nerves are respected(image3).

The extension assessment was negative. A biopsy was carried out in favor of an immunohistochemistry epithelioid sarcoma with the following characteristics: bland polygonal cells with an eosinophilic cytoplasm and peripheral fuselage. They regularly express the vimentin, cytokeratins, the antigen of the epithelial membrane and the CD34, while staining is negative with S100, desmin and FLI-1.

After multidisciplinary meeting, the patient underwent type R0 oncological resection on an anterior approach in order to control the vasculo-nervous relationship of the tumour, followed by radiotherapy.

The death occurred 9 months after surgery.

Image 1: géant tumor of the thigh

Image 2 : another clinical image of epithéioide sarcoma

Image 3 : MRI shows an antero-lateral mass of two thirds of the left thigh

II. DISCUSSION

The sarcomas of soft tissues represent 1% of all malignant tumors, the epithelioid component is even rarer among sarcomas and represents only 1% of cases(1)(2)

It preferentially affects young male adults(1).

Very few cases have been reported in the literature

MRI determines the size, reports and local extension of the tumor(3)

Biopsy with immunohistochemistry remains the main means of diagnosis.

Surgical treatment remains the only therapeutic means supplemented by radiotherapy(1)(3).

The evolution is characterized by local recurrence and locoregional and general extension(1)(2)(3).

III. CONCLUSION

Epithelioid sarcoma is a rare malignant tumor whose vital prognosis is unfavorable(1)(2), immunohistochemistry is the key examination for positive diagnosis(1)(3).

The treatment is mainly surgical and must be oncological, a supplement by radiotherapy can be proposed(1)(3).

Monitoring must be compared because the recurrence rate is very high (1)(2)(3)

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